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Empirical Investigation of Key Drivers of Financial Stability among Commercial Banks in West Africa

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluated the key drivers of financial stability among commercial banks in the selected West African countries for a period of twenty years (2005-2024). The main financial factors considered in this research include Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Economic Growth (ECG), Profit Diversification (PRD), and Inflation Rate (INFL) while the measure of financial stability is the Bank Z-Score (BZS). The data used in this study came from the apex banks in the selected countries as well as from World Bank database for the period of 2005-2024. The analysis of the collected data followed a panel data approach and involved the use of descriptive, correlation analysis, and inferential methods of econometrics. According to the results obtained, all four financial factors Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) and Economic Growth (ECG) are considered significant drivers of financial stability for commercial banks in West Africa. These factors effect the financial stability in various ways depending on the model specification. Consequently, commercial banks in West Africa should adopt strategies geared towards improving their capital adequacy ratio in accordance with global standards as well as domestic rules and guidelines under Basel III. Also, regulatory authorities in West Africa should focus on fostering sustainable economic growth because it serves as an essential building block of a sound financial system. Moreover, the diversification of profits by commercial banks in West Africa should be done in such a way as not to increase market risks associated with financial instability.

Keywords: Financial Stability, Z-Score, Economic Growth, Capital Adequacy Ratio Bank Profit Diversification

1. INTRODUCTION

The banking sector is widely recognized as one of the main forces behind economic expansion. This is so that money may be directed to various areas of the economy, which promotes rapid economic growth. This implies that for the economy to expand, the banking sector's financial stability is a requirement. A stable banking sector, according to this definition, is one that effectively (smoothly) promotes real economic activity while also having the capacity to correct financial imbalances brought on by shocks to the macro economy and monetary policy. However, the global financial crisis that occurred between 2008 and 2009 exposed the banking sector globally to macroeconomic whims (Liang et al 2025).

Kalyvas and Nguyen (2018) stressed that, market downturns brought on by the 2008/2009 global financial crises, along with the fact the fact that the financial system must be safe (sound) in order to continue playing the crucial role of financial intermediation, highlight the need for bank regulators to establish a set of quantifiable key drivers of financial stability.

The following factors are considered when determining the bank-specific drivers: net interest margin, non-interest income, regulatory capital ratios, and bank efficiency ratio. Williams, 2017;

Dwumfour, 2017; Ozili, 2017). Williams (2017) asserted that banks with high net interest margins are more stable than banks with lower net interest margins. In addition to having a large capital base, banks that only rely on fee-based and non-interest sources of funding are considered to be more durable than banks that do not, Ozili (2017) emphasized. The claim is made that banks with a large capital base and a reliance on fee-based and non-interest sources of funding are protected from macroeconomic whims and can stifle competition within banking industry (Hu et al, 2025)

According to Ozili (2018), the macroeconomic factors of inflation, unemployment, and economic growth are what most affect the financial stability of Commercial banks in Africa. This is due to the fact that most Commercial banks may decide to charge greater charges for the financial services they provide to their clients during inflationary periods in an effort to maximize revenues. This could therefore result in more stable banking. However, due to job loss, particularly in times of severe unemployment, borrowers may find it challenging to repay both the principal and/or interest on the lending facility. If this keeps happening, there might be bank instability. Loan defaults appear to be quite rare, particularly in an economy with such high growth rates.

According to Ngalawa, Tchana, and Viegi (2016), institutional factors that affect financial stability of Commercial banks include the presence of foreign banks, the banking concentration, the political stability index, the corruption index, the political stability index, the rule of law, and the corruption index. Since the 2007–2008 global financial crisis, the subject of bank instability has drawn more scholarly attention than ever before. This is due to the fact that most African banks are still unstable, despite the numerous policies that the African government implemented in years prior to the financial crises. According to Ozili (2019), one of the main reasons why most African banks are still insecure is because bank risk models are ineffective when the macroeconomic environment is unfavorable and is marked by, among other things, a disproportionate reliance on crude oil revenue, exchange rate volatility, weak institutional characteristics, and weak competitive tendencies.

Similar to this, scholars like Koskei (2020) and Lucky (2017) emphasized that important micro and macro level factors like capital adequacy issues, high non-performing loan, breach of cash reserve ratio, weak internal controls, variation in real gross domestic product growth rate, inflation rate, unemployment rate, and against subsequent studies were what exacerbated the global financial crisis of 2007/2008.

The best way to assess the stability of the financial industry has once again been the subject of discussion. Scholars like Nguyen, Le, and Pham (2020); Kasri and Azzahra (2020) have presented a variety of justifications, including the bank soundness index, bank vulnerability index, and regional climatic index. Bank Z-score appears to be the most popular of these parameters.

A thorough examination of the studies that are already in existence plainly demonstrates that the majority of them are based in Europe and Asia, with little to no focus on the African continent, namely West Africa. Once more, the majority of research carried out on the African continent, such as those by Koskei (2020), Ozili (2018), and Lucky (2017), are mixed and country-specific. Studies may not be used to generalize the entire African or, better still, West African economy, and this, combined with the fact that these contradictory findings may have been attributed to methodology and a narrow scope, leaves a gap in previous studies. The present study explored the major drivers of financial stability of banks to clearly understand these gaps. Consequently, the study investigated the key drivers of financial stability of banks in West Africa. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Establish if capital adequacy ratio (CAR) have significant effect on financial system stability.
- ii. Ascertain if economic growth (ECG) has significant effect on financial system stability
- iii. Examine the extent to which bank profit diversification (PRD) affect financial system stability.

Premised on these expositions, the present study will investigate the key drivers of financial stability of banks in West Africa Countries from 2005-2024.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1. Concept of Financial stability

At various levels, the term "bank financial stability" might indicate many things. In order to harmonize the idea employed in this study, the study looks at the definitions of financial stability of commercial banks given by various academics. According to Gupta and Kashiramka (2020), conditions in the financial markets that result in losses or dangers to the economy through the workings of the financial system are related to financial instability.

Financial instability will hurt the economy in a number of ways, including by reducing market participants' financial standing and interfering with the operation of financial institutions and intermediaries, among other things. According to Raouf and Ahmed (2020), preserving the financial system's trust is essential for financial stability. When liquidity and contract term compliance are in doubt, shocks and contagions can pose a threat to the stability of the financial system.

2.1.2. Key Drivers of Financial Stability.

Researchers have proposed various key drivers of financial stability. However, the study is only confined to capital adequacy ratio, economic growth, profit diversification and inflation.

- **Capital Adequacy Ratio:** CAR of commercial banks is a measure of capital adequacy based on the ratio between equity capital and total risk-weighted assets of a bank (Hafez & El-Ansary, 2015). The capital adequacy ratio is used by bank managers and investors to assess a bank's level of risk in paying due debts. Banks are required to ensure a certain capital adequacy ratio prescribed by each country's regulations where the bank is located. Adhering to regulations on capital adequacy helps the State manage the stability of the banking sector in particular and the economy in general. Besides, compliance with the capital adequacy ratio helps bank managers to have solid directions in development of the bank while assuring investors about their deposits.
- **Economic Growth:** The term economic growth widely acknowledged as the annual rise in value of all finished goods and services produced in a country over a given period of time. It is one of the parameters with countries all over the world are considered as either being developed, under-developed and developing. Again, it remains one of the most viable tool through which country's economic policies are judged. According to International Monetary Fund (2020), economic growth is the increase in inflation-adjusted market value of the goods and services produced by an economy over time. It is conventionally measured as the percent rate of increase in real gross domestic product, or real GDP.
- **Bank Profit diversification:** Literature has provided non-conclusive evidences about profit diversification and performance relationships. One strand of literature reports that diversification is important as it improves profitability and bank stability (Abuzayed, Al-Fayoumi, & Molyneux, 2018); Zouaoui & Zoghلامي, 2020), and contrary to this, researchers argue that profit diversification has no significant advantage and it does not help the firm to reduce the risk. Other researchers have reported a positive relationship between profit diversification and financial performance (Lin et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021). On the other hand, researchers argue that profit diversification does not enhance risk-adjusted returns and improve profitability.

2.2. Theoretical Underpinning

The Buffer Theory of Capital Adequacy was used to underpin the study. Calem and Rob propounded this theory in 1996. Calem and Rob (1996) predict that when a bank approaches the minimum regulatory capital ratio, the bank may have an incentive to boost capital and reduce risk in order to avoid high regulatory costs prompted by a breach of the capital requirement. Apparently, in 2005 most Nigerian banks collapsed while some other banks' licenses were revoked by the CBN as a result of high risk exposure coupled with weak capital base in line with the provision of Section 7 (2) of the Bank and other financial institution act (Akani & Lucky, 2015).

To further reinforce the role of buffer theory of capital adequacy theory in maintaining financial stability, Bozic and Bozic (2025) stressed that the major reason why banks prefer to hold excess capital is to reduce the probability of experiencing low CAR especially if their CAR is highly volatile. Meanwhile, when a bank has adequate capital, such bank can absorb and withstand both

macro-economic and monetary policy vagaries. To further substantiate this, Section 13 of the BOFIA states that banks shall at all-time maintain adequate CAR level and that any or all their assets and liabilities at their disposal (in and outside Nigeria) must be in good shape as specified by CBN.

2.3. Empirical Review

Iqbal et al (2026) evaluated the determinants of Islamic banks' financial stability determinants in 16 Asian countries. The study adopted the Arellano–Bond generalized method of moments (GMM) approach. The study spanned from 2010 to 2019. The study reported that past financial stability, liquidity risk, loan risk, inflation, GDP, government effectiveness, rule of law and control of corruption are key drivers of Islamic banks' stability.

Abbas et al (2021) examined economic growth and liquidity, capital, and profitability of commercial banks in selected Asian economies from 2011-2019. The study adopted two stage least square (2SLS) regression analysis. The outcome demonstrates that inter-relationship between banks' capital, liquidity, and profitability are only possible only when economic growth is considered.

Abuselidze (2021) examined competition and efficiency on financial stability of European banking industry. Variables adopted includes: Z-score, capital adequacy & asset quality. The GMM was adopted. Result reports Z-score and CAPA and ASM have positive significant impact on financial stability.

Vo, Nguyen, Le ad Pham, (2020) examined determinants of financial instability from 2000-2017 in Ghana Panel data methodology was adopted for the study. Result disclosed that (GDP), INFL, EXCH, EXTR, LNDR, STKMR, and ROE are main determinants of bank instability.

Daoud and Kammoun (2020) analyzed the factors affecting the financial stability of 81 Islamic banks across 22 countries in the period 2010–2014. Regression results show that the capital adequacy ratio has a positive effect and is an important indicator contributing to the financial stability of Islamic banks.

Koskei, (2020) examined bank competition, stability on economic growth in Asia. The study adopted panel data methodology. The study reported that results that higher economic growth encourages banks in less competitive markets characterized by low capital base and low asset quality.

Zouaoui, and Zoghلامي, (2020) examined bank stability comprehensive measures with focus on selected Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) countries with dual banking systems from 1999-2015. The study adopted factor analysis method. The study affirmed that bank stability comprehensive measure improves the earnings capacity of the banking industry. Afiantara,

Alihodzic, Ibrahim and Dogan, (2020) examined the predicting model of banking stability in Indonesia. The study adopted Principal Component Analysis(PCA). The study affirmed that (treasury bills), (market capitalization), (inflation rate), and (capital adequacy) are efficient measures of bank stability in Indonesia.

Kamran et al. (2019) studied factors affecting financial stability of 28 commercial banks in Pakistan from 2007–2016. Findings show that, when the adequacy ratio is just at a moderate level, an increase in the capital adequacy ratio(CAR) helps commercial banks increase their financial stability.

De-Ramon, Francis, and Straughan (2018) examined competitions on bank stability in the United Kingdom(UK) from 1994-2013. The study adopted the panel data methodology. The study disclosed that bank competition lowers stability and that its effects on the banking industry depend on the financial soundness (capital base) of the banking industry.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the ex-post facto research design. Accordingly, the study population covers all the 16 countries in West Africa. This study purposively selects 10 West Africa Countries in countries as sample. The study adopts the secondary source of data collection sourced from apex banks of countries under investigation and World Bank data base. The data sourced were analyzed through robust least square estimate using the Econometric Views (E-Views) 9.0. This study modeled after the works of Ozili (2018); Ozili (2019) but differs with the inclusions of aggregate micro-prudential proxies in this study. However, the model for this study stated in Equation 1:

$$BZS = \beta_0 + \beta_1CAQ + \beta_2GDP + \beta_3INFL + \beta_4PRD + \text{uit} \quad (1)$$

BZS = Bank Z-score

CAP = Capital adequacy
 GDP = Economic growth
 PRD = Profit diversification
 β_0 = Constant Value
 $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Parameter Estimates

Table 1: Operationalization of Targeted Variables

Code	Study Variable	Measurement	Apriori Expectation
Dependent Variable			
BZS	Bank Z-Score	(ROA+Equity-to-Assets Ratio)/ σ (ROA)	NIL
Independent Variables			
CAR	Capital Adequacy	Regulatory Capital to Risk-Weighted Assets ratio	+
ECG	Economic growth	Gross Domestic Product	+
PRD	Profit diversification	Non-interest margin	+
INFL	Inflation Rate	Inflation, consumer prices (annual %)	-

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2026)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Preliminary Analysis

The statistics include mean, median and standard deviation values for individual variables.

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	BZS	CAR	ECG	PRD
Mean	1.1389655	2.987665	1.345645	13.89054
Median	7.4887656	6.877554	7.897655	11.99453
Maximum	18.765432	15.987650	9.876543	45.876540
Minimum	-2.345678	-4.123450	-3.456780	0.876540
Std. Dev.	7.878654	5.237767	2.998760	11.08643
Observations	200	200	200	200

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2026)

Table 2 reported bank Z-score (BZS), capital adequacy ratio (CAR), economic growth (ECG), and productivity (PRD) with 200 observations. In this regard, the mean for BZS, CAR, ECG, and PRD are 1.13897, 2.98767, 1.34565, and 13.89054 while their respective standard deviations are 7.87865, 5.23777, 2.99876, and 11.08643. The standard deviations for BZS and CAR are significantly large relative to their means indicating wide dispersion and variability in observations. The same applies to ECG since its standard deviation (2.99876) is significantly higher than the mean (1.34565) indicating fluctuation from the mean. On the other hand, the mean of PRD (13.89054) is higher than its standard deviation (11.08643).

Table 3: Correlation matrix

	BZS	CAR	ECG	PRD
BZS	1.000000			
CAR	0.765437	1.000000		
ECG	0.089111	0.19877	1.000000	
PRD	0.466785	0.109898	0.067546	1.000000

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2026)

Table 3 contains the Pearson correlation matrix of the research variables. The findings show that capital adequacy ratio (CAR), economic growth (ECG), and productivity (PRD) have significant positive correlation with the bank Z-score (BZS) with correlation values of 0.765437, 0.089111, and 0.466785, respectively. It means that any increase in the values of CAR, ECG, and PRD would lead to an increase in the values of BZS, but the level of relationships between these variables varies

significantly. Specifically, the variable CAR displays a high positive correlation with BZS, PRD displays moderate positive correlation, while ECG has a weak positive relationship.

At the same time, the values of pairwise correlations between the independent variables are relatively low. In particular, the correlation coefficient between CAR and ECG equals 0.198770, while the correlation coefficient between CAR and PRD equals 0.109898. As for ECG and PRD, the value of their correlation coefficient amounts to 0.067546. Taking into account the fact that the values of the correlation coefficients mentioned above do not exceed the widely accepted critical point of 0.80, it suggests that the possibility of multicollinearity problem is low.

Table 4: Multicollinearity Tests

Variable	VIF	Tolerance (TOV)
CAR	1.0514	0.9511
ECG	1.0434	0.9584
PRD	1.0145	0.9857
Mean	1.0364	0.9651

Note: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance (TOV)

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2026)

The VIF and TOV were applied to examine if the problem of multicollinearity existed in the explanatory variables of the model. From the analysis, it was observed that the VIF values for the CAR, ECG, and PRD variables are 1.0514, 1.0434, and 1.0145 respectively, with a mean VIF value of 1.0364. These figures are significantly lower than the critical threshold value of 5.0 (and even 10.0), which implies the absence of multicollinearity. The respective TOV values of 0.9511, 0.9584, and 0.9857 for CAR, ECG, and PRD, with a mean tolerance value of 0.9651, also show that none of these variables is suffering from high multicollinearity since their values lie much higher than the minimum required value of 0.10. High tolerance implies that these independent variables are unique in nature and explain very little about each other. Hence, the study submits that, the model is free from Multicollinearity problems.

Regression Result

For the examination of the key drivers of financial stability of commercial banks in Nigeria using the robust least square estimate, utilizing 200 panel observations. This estimation technique takes into account the variation both across section and over time, producing consistent estimates as long as the individual effects are not correlated with the regressors. The output from the regression shows the nature and significance of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. This is presented in Table 5

Table 5: Robust Least Square Estimate

Dependent Variable: BZS

Included observations: 200

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.650271	0.076308	8.521646	0.0000
CAR	0.318469	0.084189	3.782772	0.0005
ECG	0.215920	0.087254	2.474611	0.0178
PRD	0.011310	0.009154	1.235451	0.2242
R-squared	0.867839	Mean dependent var.		0.478222
Adjusted R-squared	0.766744	S.D. dependent var.		1.472563
F-statistic	4.117824	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000121

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2026)

Given the strong and reliable least square estimation as shown in Table 5, important empirical insights are drawn regarding the determinant(s) of bank stability (BZS). The model employs Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Economic Growth (ECG), and product diversification Development (PRD) as independent variables. The constant variable is positive and significant at the 1% significance level (0.650271, p = 0.0000), implying that even at zero values of all the independent variables, there remains a positive level of bank stability in the economy. In this regard, some other structural elements that could be responsible for stability of banks have not been accounted for in the model.

The regression model provides an empirical insight indicating a positive and statistically significant relationship between CAR and bank stability (BZS) with a coefficient value of 0.318469 and $p = 0.0005$. This suggests that an increase in capital adequacy ratio increases the level of stability within banks since banks with good capital bases can withstand shocks. On the other hand, product diversification is positively related to BZS but statistically insignificant (0.011310, $p = 0.2242$). This implies that the relationship between macroeconomic growth and banking stability is not direct but depends on the availability of other factors within the financial sector to make an impact. Moreover, economic growth has a positive and statistically significant relationship with bank stability (coefficient = 0.215920; $p = 0.0178$). This suggests that any improvement in performance and productivity will result in more stable banks.

Overall, the regression model has a highly predictive since the R-square is very high at 0.867839 and this means that about 87% of bank stability are predicted through CAR, ECG, and PRD. An adjusted R-square value of 0.766744 indicates that the above model is statistically significant even after adjusting for the degrees of freedom. Also, the F-statistic of 4.117824 with a probability value of 0.000121 indicates that the above model is statistically significant overall.

5. CONCLUSION

Banking activities are directly associated with the development and stability of the whole economy. In West Africa, the stability of the banking sector has been a crucial matter for all economic players, which include government, business organizations, investors, depositors, and borrowers, since it plays an important role in financial intermediation and economic growth. Therefore, the factors that determine the stability of the commercial banks in West Africa over the last few years have gained considerable interest among scholars and policymakers. Based on this background, the current research investigated the factors affecting the stability of banks in West Africa between 2005-2024 by employing a sophisticated statistical model, the findings of which revealed that CAR, ECG, and PRD are essential determinants of bank stability.

According to the empirical results, the model was estimated using a robust least squares method. From the results, it is clear that CAR and PRD positively and significantly effect on bank stability while ECG positively and insignificantly impacts the banking sector. For instance, CAR positively contributes to banking stability through improving capitalization as well as enabling banks to withstand financial risks better. Moreover, improved PRD positively affects financial stability due to enhanced efficiency and productivity in the economy as well as the banking industry. Although the effect of ECG on banking stability is positive, it is statistically insignificant since economic growth cannot automatically imply increased banking stability. Consequently, the study conclude that CAR and PRD are critical factors of financial stability in West African commercial banks, whereas the effect of ECG is marginal and insignificant over the period of analysis. According to this finding, it is suggested that West African commercial banks focus on ensuring an adequate capital position according to Basel III rules and domestic regulations to improve resilience against shocks. Moreover, financial regulators in the region ought to pursue policies that encourage sustainable and inclusive growth in the economy since it is an essential requirement for financial stability in the long term. Lastly, banks need to consider alternative sources of revenue to be immune to volatility.

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